

ADHESIVE BONDING OF Al_2O_3 / 6061 ALUMINUM METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITES

J. Doesburg, S. H. J. Lo, G. J. C. Carpenter
MTL/CANMET, Department of Natural Resources
568 Booth St., Ottawa, Ontario K1A 0G1
Canada

ABSTRACT

A great deal of research has been reported on the adhesive bonding of aluminum alloys, but relatively little work has been performed on metal-matrix composites (MMCs), such as aluminum reinforced by alumina (Al_2O_3) particulates. In this work, a group of lap-shear specimens containing 0, 10 and 20 vol% Al_2O_3 particulate were prepared, etched in a sulphuric acid / sodium dichromate solution, and then anodized in either chromic or phosphoric acid. These specimens were subsequently glued using conventional epoxy cements, followed by lap-shear testing. It was found that the Al_2O_3 /6061 aluminum composites performed well and, in most cases, even better than the base 6061 aluminum alloy in the lap-shear tests. It is possible that the improved results in the MMC's may be due to the etching process, which preferentially attacks the interface between the particles and the matrix, increasing the surface roughness to the benefit of the adhesive bonding process. It is evident from these preliminary results that adhesive bonding may be a viable method of bonding Al_2O_3 /6061 aluminum composites.

INTRODUCTION

Adhesive bonding has replaced more conventional methods of joining metals, such as welding and riveting, in a growing number of applications. This trend is particularly prevalent in the aerospace industry, where a good deal of experience has been acquired from the extensive use of adhesives in joining aluminum alloys. As the use of metal-matrix composites (MMC's) increases in industry, reliable methods of joining these materials must be found. This work focused on the suitability of using adhesive bonding to join an MMC consisting of a 6061 aluminum matrix reinforced with alumina (Al_2O_3) particulate.

There are a large number of advantages which can make adhesive bonding an attractive method of joining materials. These advantages include [1,2,3,4] good corrosion and fatigue resistance, the retention of adherend properties, joint stiffness, the ability to join dissimilar materials, the sealing of the joint area, and a smoother external surface. Some problems associated with adhesive bonding are joint strength, durability of the bond, the large number of fabrication and handling steps necessary for production, and quality assurance. In situations where adhesive bonding is used, the bond area is made large enough to overcome the low relative strength of adhesives. The durability of an adhesive bond can be greatly enhanced by proper preparation of the adherend surface [5,6,7].

SURFACE PREPARATION

Aluminum surfaces can be prepared for gluing by subjecting them to an acid etch, followed by an anodizing treatment, in order to create a porous oxide structure on the aluminum surface that is able to enhance adhesion and increase the lifetime of the bond[5,6,7]. The oxide produced by these treatments is believed to be boehmite[8], changing to bayerite with traces of gibbsite after aging in water[9,10].

The initial stage of surface preparation involves grit blasting or fine sanding to give the adherend a rough surface. In MMC's it was observed[11] that grit blasting removed some of the particulate and smeared the aluminum matrix over other particles, resulting in an aluminum-rich surface. This was followed by degreasing with an organic solvent to remove surface contamination. The cleaned metal surfaces could then be successfully bonded, but with a great cost to durability. It is therefore common practice to etch and anodize the adherend surfaces.

The most common etching solution used for aluminum surface preparation is the FPL (Forest Products Laboratories) etch, although an alternative etch, using a sodium hydroxide solution is also sometimes used. The FPL etching solution is made up of sodium dichromate and sulphuric acid, and creates a very fine oxide structure[12] about 50Å thick, in addition to leaving the surface with fine scallops[13], 0.4 - 1.5µm across. In the case of MMC's, it has been found that the FPL etching solution causes the formation of craters[11,14,15] around the reinforcing particulates/fibres at the surface, liberating some of them. This is due to a preferential attack of the interface between the particles/fibres and the aluminum matrix by the etching solution.

The last surface preparation step involves anodizing the surface of the adherend. The two most common techniques used for aluminum are phosphoric acid anodizing (PAA) and chromic acid anodizing (CAA). An alternative, sometimes used, involves sulphuric acid anodizing (SAA) followed by a phosphoric acid dip (PAD).

Each of the anodizing techniques creates a different oxide structure. Phosphoric acid forms a 'forest' of rod-like protrusions that rise perpendicular to the surface[16], chromic acid forms a honeycomb structure, whilst sulphuric acid forms a thicker, relatively featureless oxide layer that is converted to a structure[11] resembling a paintbrush following the phosphoric acid dip. As well as creating different types of oxide structures, the different anodizing treatments result in structures which incorporate the electrolyte anions[17].

The effect of anodizing treatments on MMC's appears to be somewhat variable. Some research[15,18] indicates that fibre damage can occur and some particles and fibres may detach from the surface as the metal is converted to oxide. The particles are then believed to interfere with the growth of the oxide columns, affecting the performance of the adhesive bond. However, Berquist et al.[11] have observed adhesive shear strengths in silicon carbide particulate-reinforced aluminum that were as strong as or even stronger than those observed in the parent material. They have proposed that during the curing of the adhesive at elevated temperature and pressure, the adhesive may displace the particles from the surface, while adhesive filling in and around cracks and crevices could create a unique interphase consisting of adhesive, aluminum oxide, silicon carbide and aluminum all joined to each other.

ADHESIVE BONDING

The object of the pretreatments described in the previous sections is to create a surface which is microscopically rough, namely with features of the order of tens of nanometers, in order to achieve efficient mechanical interlocking between the adhesive and the surface[6]. The surface roughness also increases the surface area and therefore the number chemical bonds between the adhesive and adherend[19,20]. Surfaces containing features with sizes in the order of micrometers are believed to be less effective than sub-microscopic roughness, as they do not contain as many interlocking sites[6]. In addition to this, there is also a greater chance of trapping contaminants and air by the surface, reducing the performance of the adhesive bond.

There has been much debate about the mechanism of adhesive bonding. The chemical bonds between the adhesive and adherend may be covalent, acid-base, van Der Waals, or hydrogen-type bonds[21], while the mechanical bonds that are possible include physical interlocking and diffusional bonds. Kollek[22], has suggested that mechanical interlocking is not able to explain the interactions between the adhesive and adherend, and chemical bonds[20] are believed to explain many of the properties of adhesive joints. Chemical bonds depend on the number of bond sites on the adherend surface, so that an increase in the surface area should result in a better adhesive bond, regardless of the effect of mechanical interlocking.

The ideas presented in the last two paragraphs are only valid if the adhesive penetrates into the pores of the oxide layer on the adherend surface. It has been reported[18,21] that there is penetration of the adhesive into the pores of the oxide prepared by both the PAA and SAA/PAD processes, whilst the oxide produced by the CAA technique results in relatively little adhesive penetration. This may help to explain the superior shear strengths reported in joints prepared by the PAA and SAA/PAD techniques, compared to the CAA method.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The hot-rolled sheet materials used in this work were Duralcan W6A-10A and W6A-20A, composed of 6061 aluminum containing 10% and 20% Al_2O_3 particulate reinforcement respectively. The rolled sheets, which had thicknesses that varied between 1.6 mm and 1.7 mm, were subsequently cut and ground into lap-shear specimens having a length of 101.6 mm and a width of 25.4 mm. A sheet of 6061 aluminum with a thickness of 1.6 mm was cut into samples having similar dimensions to the composite specimens using mechanical shears. After the specimens were prepared to the correct dimensions, they were all given a T6 heat treatment for precipitation hardening.

Following the heat treatment, the samples were prepared for anodization by first grinding using 80, 180 and 320 grit SiC papers and then degreasing by initially placing them in an ultrasonic bath of alcohol for 1-2 min.. This was followed by an immersion in an acetone bath after which the samples were dried. The last step of preparation involved the placing of samples in a 1,1,1 trichloroethane bath and dried. Each sample was tested for a water break, and samples that passed the test were dried using a heat gun and stored for anodization.

All the samples were etched using the FPL etch for 10-15 min. at 66°C-71°C in a solution composed of 300g/l H_2SO_4 , 50g $Na_2Cr_2O_7(2H_2O)$ and >1.5g of 6061 Al. Two different anodization methods were employed in this experiment. Half of the samples were anodized using the phosphoric acid anodization treatment developed by Boeing, in a stainless steel beaker containing a solution composed of 10% phosphoric acid for a time of 25 minutes, at a temperature of 25°C and a voltage of 10V. The other half of the samples were anodized for 30 minutes in a chromic acid bath (containing 10wt% CrO_3), at a temperature of 33°C-37°C, with a voltage of 40V. After anodizing, the samples were rinsed for 10-15 minutes, checked for water break, and dried in hot air for 5-10 minutes.

The structure of the anodized surfaces was examined using small bulk specimens in a Philips CM20FEG transmission/scanning electron microscope equipped with a field-emission gun, operated at 200kV in secondary-electron scanning mode. The surfaces were rendered conductive by the deposition of a thin film of Pt using ion-beam sputtering.

The last part of the experiment involved the gluing and testing of the samples. Four epoxy adhesives and one polyamide adhesive were used; after a series of preliminary tests, two epoxies, Cybond FM 300K epoxy film and 3M Scotch Weld 1386 one-part epoxy were selected for more extensive testing. The specimens were glued following the manufacturers guidelines. The overlap on the samples was between 13 mm and 16 mm, and the samples were held together by four small steel spring clips to ensure an approximately equal pressure on all of the specimens. The shear strengths were measured by tensile loading in an Instron 8562 testing machine, using the ASTM D1002-72 testing standard.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Scanning electron microscopy at low magnifications showed evidence of substantial pit formation at the particulate/matrix interfaces in all specimens (figure 1). With a finely-focussed probe from the field-emission gun, it was possible to obtain surface images showing excellent resolution at magnifications up to $\sim 150,000\times$. The sample anodized in phosphoric acid was covered with rod-like protrusions with diameters 10–100nm and heights estimated to be ~ 100 nm (figure 2). The chromic acid etch resulted in a smoother surface, containing pores 7–50nm in diameter with a mean spacing estimated to be ~ 30 nm (figure 3). In addition to the surface irregularities from the particulate and the fine surface structure of the oxide, there were also intermediate irregularities from the etching of both the matrix and the intermetallic particles in all specimens.

Figure 1. Scanning electron micrograph showing the formation of coarse pits around Al_2O_3 particulates in a 6061 Al alloy MMC, after etching.

Figure 2. High-magnification image showing a high surface density of rod-like protrusions on a 20vol% particulate MMC, anodized in a phosphoric acid bath.

Figure 3. Surface cavities on the surface of a 20vol% particulate MMC, anodized in a chromic acid bath.

The results of the lap-shear tests on samples using the Cybond FM 300K epoxy film and the 3M Scotch Weld 1386 one part epoxy are given in Table 1. It can be concluded that the shear stress to failure increases as the amount of particulate reinforcement present in the metal matrix increases. When comparing the results from the samples anodized in phosphoric acid and those anodized in chromic acid for the 3M Scotch Weld 1386 epoxy, it can be seen that the phosphoric acid anodization produced a slightly stronger bond than the chromic acid anodization.

Table 1. Lap-Shear Test Results

Glue	Anodizing Method	Vol.% Al ₂ O ₃ Particulate	Average Shear Stress (MPa)
Cybond® FM® 300 Epoxy Film	PAA	0	31.99
		10	32.84
		20	33.68
3M Scotch Weld 1386 One Part Epoxy	PAA	0	33.64
		10	36.66
		20	37.31
	CAA	0	31.22
		10	35.82
		20	36.43

A possible explanation for the increase of tensile shear strength with increasing particulate concentration is found in the etching stage, in addition to the surface morphology of the anodized coatings. Figure 1 shows that the FPL etch preferentially attacks the particle/matrix interfaces, leaving pits which surround the particles, as observed in other studies[11,14,15]. The pits result in a significant increase in localized surface roughness on a scale of many micrometers. It appears that the formation of these pits leads to a greater surface area for the adhesive to form chemical and mechanical bonds, ultimately resulting in an increase in tensile shear strengths as the number density of particles present in the MMC increases.

In the case of the 3M One Part Epoxy, a small but significant increase in bond strength was realised by using the phosphoric anodizing process rather than the chromic acid solution. This must be ascribed to the increased roughness of the PAA anodized surface, on a scale of nanometers, which nonetheless leads to a substantial increase in surface area.

CONCLUSIONS

MMC's made up of Al₂O₃ particulates in a 6061 Al alloy matrix performed as well or better than the un-reinforced matrix alloy with respect to tensile shear strength. There was a significant increase in shear strength as the amount of particulate reinforcement increased. It is believed that this result is due to the preferential attack by the preliminary etching treatment at the particle/matrix interfaces, resulting in a rougher surface topography, thus increasing the amount of chemical and mechanical interlocking between the adhesive and the adherend. A small but significant improvement in bond strength was observed using phosphoric acid anodizing compared to a chromic acid bath. It can be concluded that adhesive bonding is a viable method of joining aluminum-based MMC's.

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